

Automated Fall Detection for Elderly Care Leveraging IoT for Safety

Samskruthi C; Spoorthi B R; Sriram R Kashyap; Sudhanva Aathreya B M; Jagadeesh B N
Department of Information Science and Engineering
RNS Institute of Technology, Bengaluru

Abstract:- With the increasing elderly population, fall detection systems have become crucial in providing timely assistance to reduce fall-related injuries and fatalities. This project presents an IoT based fall detection system designed to monitor aged individuals in real-time, identifying sudden falls through wearable sensors and environmental data. By leveraging accelerometers, gyroscopes, and sense motions, the system detects abrupt changes in posture or unusual movements indicative of a fall. Upon detection, the system immediately sends notifications to caregivers or emergency contacts, providing real-time alerts along with location information to facilitate quick intervention. This solution makes things safer and helps families and caregivers feel more at ease and caregivers, offering a reliable, efficient, and scalable approach to elderly care using IoT technology.

Keywords:- *IoT-Based Fall Detection, Elderly Safety, Wearable Sensors, Real-Time Monitoring, Accelerometer And Gyroscope, Emergency Alert System, Elder Care Technology, Posture Detection, Caregiver Notification, Health Monitoring*

I. INTRODUCTION

Falling can lead to major injuries in aged/older individuals, often leading to serious injuries, loss of independence, and a significant decline in quality of life. With the global population aging rapidly, there is an increasing need for reliable systems that can detect falls promptly and ensure rapid assistance. This project introduces an Internet of Things (IoT)-based fall detection system that consists of sensors that include accelerometers and gyroscopes, to detect patterns of motion in real time. By identifying swift changes in body posture or motion, indicative of a potential fall or descend, the system promptly triggers alerts sent to caregivers or emergency contacts, enabling swift intervention. Through continuous, automated monitoring, this solution not only enhances safety but also provides peace of mind for families and caregivers. This approach leverages advancements in IoT to create a scalable, efficient, and accessible means of supporting elderly individuals, contributing to a proactive approach in elderly healthcare and injury prevention.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Overview of the literature survey is essential because it looks at different analyses. It explores every corner of the earlier works that has been released, taking into account various project characteristics and the project's scope. A literature review's main aim is to look into the project's history in detail, pointing out flaws in the current setup explains how things are arranged and points out areas that still need improvement. It discusses the project's background and highlights the problems and limitations that inspired the project, along with suggestions to solve these issues.

➤ *Fall Detection System for Elderly People using IoT and Big Data:*

Diana Yacchiremaa,b,, Jara Suárez de Pugaa , Carlos Palaua , Manuel Esteve, — Falls are a critical health risk for elderly individuals worldwide, often leading to severe consequences if help is not provided quickly. This work presents a cutting-edge system of fall detection based on IoT, designed to monitor aged individuals in indoor settings. By integrating big data, smart devices, cloud technology and wireless sensor networks with low power, the system achieves high accuracy in detecting falls. This data is processed through a big data model on a smart IoT gateway based on decision tree, ensuring effective and timely detection of fall. When a fall is detected, system automatically sends alerts to designated caregivers. Additionally, the system's cloud component enables healthcare providers to access detailed fall records, allowing further analysis and updates to the machine learning model based on new data. Experimental results show high performance in detection accuracy and reliability, highlighting the system's potential to improve elderly care through innovative technology.

➤ *A Survey of IoT-Based Fall Detection for Aiding Elderly Care*

Mohamed Esmail Karar, Hazem Ibrahim Shehata and Omar Reyad -. One of the most notable applications is real-time detection of incidents involving falling of elderly individuals. This article reviews recent studies focused on developing AI methods and algorithms for fall-detection systems within IoT environments. It also discusses the role of different sensors, such as accelerometers and gyroscopes in smartwatches, while addressing the limitations and challenges in achieving effective FDS solutions.

The article highlights the issue of the scarcity of publicly available fall datasets for testing these detection algorithms. Finally, it concludes by recommending improved methods, such as lightweight models, as potential solutions, aiming to look towards the future of IoT-based systems for accurate detection of fall in aged people.

➤ *Enhancing Elderly Fall Detection through IoT- Enabled Smart Flooring and AI for Independent Living Sustainability:*

Hatem A. Alharbi , Khulud K. Alharbi and Ch Anwar Ul Hassan-Falls among elderly individuals living alone can lead to serious consequences, such as complications after the fall, making timely fall detection essential. This topic of study presents a novel elder fall detection system that integrates AI technologies and IoT to improve the safety of elderly people. Experiments with 13 participants were conducted to simulate fall events, where the RFID tags sent signals to the readers, allowing the system to distinguish between falls and normal movements. Results revealed that the Random Forest algorithm had a 43% accuracy, GRUs achieved 44%, and XGBoost reached 33%. However, KNN excelled with an accuracy of 99%. This research aims to propose an effective fall detection system that enhances the safety and well-being of elderly individuals living independently, while also supporting sustainable IoT and AI solutions for healthcare.

➤ *Elder Assist - An IoT Based Fall Detection System:*

Prashant Wakhare , Hrishikesh Tavar , Priyanka Jagtap, Mayur Rane , Harshvardhan Waghmare-With the increasing global population, there is an urgent need for advanced fall detection systems, especially for elderly individuals, as falls can have serious and life-altering consequences. The rapid advancements in sensor technologies and the Internet of Things (IoT) have made human-computer interaction through sensor fusion a promising solution to address fall detection and provide immediate assistance. This paper introduces a solution by proposing an IoT-based device integrated into a walking stick, a common tool for elderly users. The device, built with sensor networks and IoT technology, is designed to aid both elderly and visually impaired individuals. The smart walking stick not only helps with fall detection but also assists in navigation, making it easier for users to move confidently and safely. The system uses an ultrasonic sensor to detect obstacles in the user's path, alerting them to any potential hazards. This enables users to navigate their surroundings without fear of encountering objects. The project also aims to enhance the functionality of this walking stick by improving its obstacle detection capabilities, ensuring a more effective navigation experience. By measuring the distance between the user and nearby obstacles, the smart walking stick can notify the user of approaching objects, helping them maintain their independence and mobility with greater ease and safety.

➤ *An IoT- Based Wearable Fall Detection System;*

Alin Anil1, Athira S, Raifa Rafi, Asst. Professor Netha Merin Mathew - Falls are a major health concern, particularly for the elderly. Older adults are more likely to

die or get seriously hurt from falls, and this risk grows as they get older. It is estimated that between 28-35% of people aged 65 and above experience a fall annually. While it may not be possible to prevent every fall, steps can be taken to minimize the risk of severe outcomes. The wearable device primarily uses a triaxial accelerometer sensor attached to the user's body to differentiate between daily activities and fall events.

Additionally, the device includes sensors that monitor vital signs such as body temperature, pulse rate, and ECG. The system combines both hardware and software to continuously detect and report falls. When a fall is detected, the system automatically alerts the designated contact and notifies the appropriate hospital, ensuring that immediate medical assistance is provided to the person in need.

➤ *A Novel Iot Based Automatic Fall Detection Cavity For Elderly People Using Mems- 1 Pedditi Satvika, 2 Parankusham Vaishnavi, 3 Mamindla Mounika, 4 Dr. K. Srujan Raju:*

Here's a reworded version of the text with different wording. If not treated promptly, falls can lead to long-term disabilities and a significant decline in an elderly person's mobility, independence, and overall well-being. The most severe effects of falls are not necessarily from the fall itself, but from delays in receiving assistance or lack of timely treatment. To improve the quality of life for elderly individuals and others in need of special care, it is crucial to have a monitoring system that can alert caregivers when emergency help is required. Recent advancements in technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT) and mobile communication have enabled the collection of data on individuals and their surroundings for various purposes. This study introduces a novel IoT-based automated fall detection system for seniors, utilizing Micro Electro-Mechanical Systems (MEMS). When a fall occurs, a low-cost detection device is used to accurately identify the incident. The fall detection algorithm works by analyzing acceleration data and comparing it against preset threshold values for both lower and upper limits. To enhance detection accuracy, a post-fall recognition module is added, which combines posture analysis with vertical velocity estimation. The system provides immediate voice alerts to the user upon detecting a fall and shows the information on an LCD screen. The data is then uploaded to the IoT server, where caregivers can monitor the situation in real time.

III. OBJECTIVES

- Develop an IoT-based fall detection system for elderly individuals using low cost Micro Electro-Mechanical Systems (MEMS) sensors.
- Implement a fall detection algorithm that analyzes acceleration data to identify fall events based on predefined threshold values.
- Alert the user immediately by providing a voice notification when a fall is detected.
- Display fall detection information on an LCD screen for quick reference.

- Upload fall detection data to an IoT server, enabling real-time monitoring by caregivers or family members.

- Improve the overall safety and well-being of elderly individuals by providing timely alerts to caregivers, reducing the response time to a fall incident.

Fig 1: Objectives of the System

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system is an IoT-based fall detection device designed for elderly individuals, using low-cost MEMS (Micro Electro- Mechanical Systems) sensors. It accurately detects falls by analyzing acceleration data against predefined threshold values. To enhance detection reliability, the system incorporates a post-fall recognition module that combines posture recognition and vertical velocity estimation. When a fall is detected, the system immediately informs the user through a voice alert and displays the information on an LCD screen. The collected data is then uploaded to an IoT server, allowing caregivers to monitor the user's status in real-time and respond promptly to any emergencies.

➤ *Sensor Data Collection:*

- The MEMS accelerometer sensor attached to the elderly individual collects real-time acceleration data.

➤ *Data Analysis:*

- The collected data is processed by the fall detection algorithm, which compares the acceleration values to predefined threshold limits.

➤ *Fall Detection:*

- If a fall is detected, the system triggers the post-fall recognition module, which uses posture recognition and vertical velocity estimation for confirmation.

➤ *User Notification:*

- Upon confirming a fall, the system sends a voice alert to notify the user about the fall event.

➤ *LCD Display:*

- The system simultaneously displays fall status for immediate visual reference.

➤ *Data Upload:*

- The system uploads the fall detection data to an IoT server for real-time monitoring by caregivers or family members.

➤ *Caregiver Alert:*

- Caregivers receive an automated message with fall detection details, allowing them to take necessary actions promptly.

➤ *Real-time Monitoring:*

- The caregiver can continuously monitor the status of the elderly individual through the IoT server, ensuring quick response and support.

V. ADVANTAGES OF THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

➤ *Enhanced Accuracy:*

Uses posture recognition and vertical velocity estimation to improve the accuracy of fall detection, minimizing false alarms.

➤ *Timely Alerts to Caregivers:*

Sends instant notifications to caregivers and family members, ensuring rapid response and assistance.

➤ *Improved Safety for Elderly Individuals:*

Increases the safety of elderly people by continuously monitoring their status and providing prompt alerts in case of falls.

➤ *User-friendly Notifications:*

Provides voice alerts and visual notifications on an LCD screen, making it easy for users to understand and respond.

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this IoT-based fall detection system offers an effective and reliable solution to address the critical need for real-time monitoring and safety assurance for elderly individuals. By integrating wearable sensors and leveraging IoT connectivity, the system successfully detects falls with high accuracy and promptly alerts caregivers, ensuring timely assistance and reducing the potential for severe health consequences. This project demonstrates the potential of IoT in advancing healthcare for the elderly, providing a scalable and accessible technology that enhances the quality of life and peace of mind for both elderly individuals and their families. Future developments could include integrating machine learning algorithms to improve detection accuracy further and expanding functionality to include predictive analytics, allowing for even more proactive health monitoring and intervention.

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